

Supplemental Material -

A Detailed Description of Statistical Methods, Pre-Analyses and Detailed Results from Linear Mixed-Effects Models

1 Statistical Methods

The two controlled sessions were compared using the Wilcoxon signed-rank test, and participant groups within each session using the Mann-Whitney U test.

To predict task completion, duration, and perceived workload, (generalized) linear mixed-effects models were used, with task categories and Copilot interaction types as fixed effects (Figure 1). For task duration, the number of in-code and chat interactions were additionally added as fixed effects to reflect interaction intensity. Participants and tasks were included as random effects to account for individual and task-level variability.

Analyses were conducted in R using the “lme4” package [4] and the functions “lmer” and “glmer”. Model assumptions (e.g. normality, homoscedasticity, no multicollinearity between fixed effects) were checked for every model. Likelihood ratio tests were conducted to compare the fit of nested models – an analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to assess the contribution of a fixed effect to the model fit on the data.

Dependent variables included task completion (completed, partly/not completed), the log-transformed task duration and the log-transformed raw NASA-TLX score (+1 to handle zero values). Log transformation reduced skewness, made variance more stable, and improved linearity and residual behavior. When the raw NASA-TLX score was used as a predictor, it was standardized for interpretability and model stability, with the average perceived workload serving as the baseline.

A post hoc Tukey test was used for pairwise comparisons between specific levels of the fixed effects. All p-values were adjusted via the Holm method to control for multiple testing errors while maintaining statistical power.

2 Pre-analyses for evaluating the controlled sessions

Before analyzing the GenAI interaction, we first need to determine how to treat the two controlled sessions and the participant groups - do the two sessions or participant groups differ significantly? Group A didn't use GenAI in the first session, while Group B did. In the second session, both used GenAI. For one participant from group B, only the screen recording from the second session could be used for analysis.

2.1 Difference between controlled sessions. Task durations across the two controlled sessions were compared within each group. For both groups, no significant differences were found. The result of Group A ($W=24$, $p=0.7695$, $r=0.1128$) suggests that not using GenAI in the first session had no impact on task duration in the second session. The result of Group B ($W=24$, $p=0.7695$, $r=0.1128$) shows no evidence of a familiarization effect between the two sessions. Given the short time span between sessions, these results are expected. Therefore, both sessions are analyzed together in the following.

2.2 Difference between groups. Within each controlled session, the groups were compared regarding total task duration, with no differences found. In the first session ($U=61$, $p=0.4274$, $r=0.263$), this indicates that GenAI use did not affect task duration, as Group A did not use GenAI while Group B did. The results of the second session ($U=43$, $p=0.6232$, $r=0.1673$) imply that prior GenAI use in the first session did not impact task duration in the second session. Therefore, the groups are thus analyzed together.

Figure 1: Predictors for the dependent variables are visualized.

3 Detailed Results from Linear Mixed-Effects Models

The following analysis examines how GenAI/ GitHub Copilot use impacts task duration (efficiency). To investigate the impact of Copilot use on task duration, linear mixed-effects models predicting the log-transformed task duration were fit on the data and compared. The impact of interaction types (without GenAI use, only in-code suggestions, only chat prompts or both in-code suggestions and chat prompts) and interaction intensity (number of in-code suggestions

and number of chat prompts) on task duration is examined. As detailed in Table 1, both interaction type and intensity significantly improve model fit, individually and combined. This suggests that how and how much developers used Copilot had an impact on the task durations.

Table 1: Impact of interaction type and interaction intensity on log task duration

Models: <i>Full model:</i> log task duration ~ interaction type + num_inCode + num_chat + task categories + scaled raw NASA-TLX + (1 participants) + (1 tasks) <i>Null model0:</i> log task duration ~ task categories + scaled raw NASA-TLX + (1 participants) + (1 tasks) <i>Null model1:</i> log task duration ~ interaction type + task categories + scaled raw NASA-TLX + (1 participants) + (1 tasks) <i>Null model2:</i> log task duration ~ num_inCode + num_chat + task categories + scaled raw NASA-TLX + (1 participants) + (1 tasks)						
Question	Model comparison	AIC	χ^2	df	p-value (adjusted p-value)	Answer
Does adding information on Copilot interaction type and interaction intensity improve log task duration prediction compared to no GenAI information?	Full model, Null model0	AIC _{full_model} =388.28, AIC _{null_model0} =406.29	28.01	5	<0.001 (<0.001)	Yes
Does information on Copilot interaction type influence the prediction of the log task duration?	Null model0, Null model1	AIC _{null_model0} =406.29, AIC _{null_model1} =399.85	12.45	3	0.006 (0.0180)	Yes
Does the amount/intensity of Copilot usage impact the prediction of the log task duration?	Null model0, Null model2	AIC _{null_model0} =406.29, AIC _{null_model2} =401.41	8.89	2	0.0118 (0.0236)	Yes
Once we know that Copilot was used, does knowing how intensively it was used improve the prediction of log task duration?	Full model, Null model1	AIC _{full_model} =388.28, AIC _{null_model1} =399.85	15.56	2	<0.001 (<0.001)	Yes
Once we know how intensively Copilot was used, does knowing the interaction type further improve the prediction of log task duration?	Full model, Null model2	AIC _{full_model} =388.28, AIC _{null_model2} =401.41	19.12	3	<0.001 (<0.001)	Yes